

EFFECTS OF MATRIX MICROSTRUCTURE ON THE FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH RESISTANCE OF TITANIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

Effects of matrix microstructure on the fatigue crack growth resistance of two continuous SiC fibre, SM1140+ and SM1240, reinforced Ti-6Al-4V composites have been addressed. For the SM1140+ fibre reinforced composite, the fully transformed beta matrix microstructure was the most resistant to fatigue crack growth. However, for the SM1240 fibre reinforced composite, heat treatments at a temperature of 1030°C and above result in a reduction in fatigue crack growth resistance. These observations are discussed here with particular reference to the morphology of the reaction layers that are produced by thermal treatments above the composite processing temperature.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing requirements of gas turbine aeroengine designs have led to ever increasing demand for materials capable of withstanding increasingly more stringent operating conditions. The potential advantages offered by composite materials compared to conventional monolithic materials include reduced weight, increased strength, and superior stiffness. The potential of metal matrix composites to withstand the mechanical and environmental conditions within the low and intermediate regions of a gas turbine engine have been considered widely [1,2,3,4]. Continuous fibre reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) are known to exhibit improved fatigue crack

growth resistance compared to equivalent monolithic materials, and recent observations have indicated that further improvements may be gained by introducing additional heat treatments. It has also been clearly established that fatigue crack growth in monolithic titanium alloys can be significantly improved by controlling microstructure. This improvement in the monolithic alloy fatigue crack growth performance should then translate to improved performance in MMCs, and this is the subject of the present study, and of which this paper presents some preliminary observations.

EXPERIMENTAL

The material used in this study was produced by D.R.A. Sigma, formerly B.P. Composites, by the foil-fibre-foil route and was received as 8 ply unidirectional composite panels (300x300x1.4 mm³). The matrix was made from foils of IMI 318 (Ti-6Al-4V). Continuous SiC (Sigma) fibres produced by chemical vapour deposition onto a tungsten core, were used to reinforce the matrix. Two fibre coatings were selected, SM1140+, a 4.5µm thick carbon coating, and SM1240, a two layer coating consisting of an inner 1µm carbon layer and a 1µm boron rich TiB_x outer layer. In all cases heat treatment was initially carried out to evaluate the beta transus approach curve for the two composite panels. To avoid oxidation during heat treatment all specimens were wrapped in tantalum foil and encapsulated subsequently in a silica tube which had been evacuated and back filled with argon. Heat treatments were conducted in a standard muffle type furnace, with a controlled heating rate of 10°C per minute from room temperature and a 10 minute hold at pre determined temperatures. All silica tubes were then air cooled from the hold temperature. Fatigue crack growth resistance was evaluated on material in both the as processed and heat treated conditions. Heat treatment conditions and fatigue crack growth arrest limits are given in table 1. All tests were conducted in three point bending with specimen dimensions approximately 75x4.5x1.4 mm³, a total loading span of 60 mm and a R ratio ($R = P_{\min}/P_{\max}$, where P_{\min} , P_{\max} are the minimum and maximum loads respectively applied over the fatigue cycle) of 0.1. Servo hydraulic test machines of 10 kN capacity were used. All tests were performed under load control at a frequency of 5 Hz. Notches were cut using a 0.15 mm thick diamond wafering blade with notches extending to a depth of 1.0-1.3 mm (i.e. an initial unbridged defect, a_0 , to width, W , ratio of $a_0/W=0.25$). Crack growth was monitored continuously during testing using the direct current potential drop technique. Crack growth rates were calculated using an incremental five point secant procedure. The conditions for crack arrest were considered here to be a growth rate below 10⁻⁷mm/cycle. The methodology of defining crack arrest conditions is given in detail elsewhere [8]. Here it is noted that a number of individual testpieces of the same size are required. They must all be pre-notched to the same depth, a_0 , and the initial stress intensity factor range is then varied to produce catastrophic failure or crack arrest on each individual testpiece. Temperature induced changes in alpha phase volume fraction were assessed using a Leica Quantimet image analyser. Metallographic studies of the extent of fibre matrix interactions were conducted using a Jeol 6300 scanning electron microscope (S.E.M.) and a Jeol 840A fitted with an energy and wavelength dispersive X-ray probes. Following fatigue crack growth tests all specimens were evaluated using metallography and fractography in order to determine both crack path morphology and the extent of crack tip and /or matrix interactions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quantitative data relating to the effects of thermal exposure and fibre type on the relative proportions of alpha and transformed beta are shown in figure 1. Included in this figure are results obtained by IMI Titanium for monolithic IMI 318. It is apparent from these results that significant variations were observed in the heat treatment response of the different materials and which result in a distinct shift in the beta transus approach curve. No precise alpha /beta transition temperature has been identified for the composite materials. However, compared to the monolithic material there is sufficient evidence to suggest the fibres incorporated into the composite have displaced the

beta transus approach curve to significantly higher temperatures. Microstructural observations indicate

Table 1. Summary of the crack arrest conditions as a function of initial ΔK applied, fibre type and prior heat treatment. All tests were carried out at room temperature and R ratio of 0.1. (Where the material has been tested in the as processed /as received condition the temperature of heat treatment is expressed as AR)

Fibre Coating System		SM1140+ (4.5 μ m carbon)				SM1240			
Heat Treatment Temperature °C		AR	950	1030	1070	AR	950	1030	1070
Applied	12								arrest
	Initial	14							fail
Stress	16	arrest				arrest		fail	fail
	Intensity	18	arrest				arrest	arrest	fail
Factor	20	arrest	arrest			fail	arrest	fail	
	Range	22	arrest	arrest	arrest			fail	fail
ΔK	25	arrest	fail	arrest				fail	
	27	fail		arrest	arrest			fail	
MPa \sqrt m	29			arrest	arrest				
	31			fail	arrest				
	33				fail				

that above a temperature of 1070°C the matrix of the composite is in a fully beta condition. From the data presented in figure 1, it would appear that the alpha beta transition temperature for the composites is in the range 1050-1060°C. This shift would be consistent with an increase in alpha stabiliser content and as such would tend to suggest some degree of fibre/matrix interaction with the possible diffusion of carbon and boron into the matrix. Such reactions would result in a depletion in the carbon and boron coating layers around the fibres with possible effects on fibre stability and strength. Micrographs illustrating the morphology of the interfacial layers formed around both the SM1140+ and SM1240 fibre are reproduced in figure 2. Distinct reaction layers were observed to develop in both materials with the extent of the reaction increasing significantly as the temperature of exposure was increased. A characteristic of the SM1140+ fibre interfacial reactions was found to be the development of continuous 'blocky' protrusions of titanium carbide,

which extend around the carbon coating layer and into the metal matrix. Electron probe micro analysis revealed the reaction layer to be carbon rich compared to stoichiometric TiC. A progressive increase in the reaction layer thickness was observed with increasing temperature, with the average thickness increasing from 0.82 μm after exposure at a temperature of 950°C up to approximately 2.90 μm after exposure at a temperature of 1100°C. The carbon layer thickness was reduced by 0.15 and 0.57 μm respectively after these heat treatments.

Figure 1, Beta transus approach curves for the matrix of 1140+ fibre and 1240 fibre composite. Also included is the beta transus curve for IMI 318.

A number of detailed studies on the SM1240 fibre TiB_x coating interfacial reactions have been conducted [6,7,8] and a good understanding of the kinetics of the fibre /matrix reactions and the morphology of the reaction products has been developed[6,7]. The present study would tend to indicate the development of a duplex reaction product, figure 2b, consisting of an inner continuous titanium and boron rich layer surrounded by a network of inter connecting needles extending into the metal matrix. Preliminary E.P.M.A. analysis would tend to suggest that these layers consist of a mixture of TiB_2 and TiB titanium borides. The extension of the outer layer of TiB needles into the matrix increased from 2.25 μm after heat treatment at a temperature of 950°C to in excess of 20 μm after heat treatment at a temperature of 1100°C. In contrast the inner TiB_2 layer exhibited very little growth with an average thickness of 1.70 μm after exposure at a temperature of 1100°C. E.P.M.A. analysis of the SM1140+ material suggested that carbon diffusion into the matrix was significant with nominal carbon concentrations reaching as high as 13 atomic percent (3.5 weight percent). Such high carbon concentrations are not normally expected in the monolithic material ($\leq 300\text{ppm}$), however the increase in alpha /beta transition temperature and the observation of blocky titanium carbides remote from the fibres in the SM1140+ material, clearly lends some support to the E.P.M.A. results. These observations concur with the concept of carbon depletion from the fibre coating and its subsequent diffusion into the metal matrix and which pushes the beta transus to higher temperatures. The kinetic features associated with carbon depletion in the carbon and boron coated SM1240 fibre material have been considered in detail [7]. These studies indicate that the outer boron rich layer after reaction with the titanium matrix effectively acts as a diffusion barrier and delays the consumption of the underlying carbon coating and its diffusion into the matrix. As indicated in table 1 fatigue crack growth studies were conducted on material in the as-received and heat treated conditions, both as a function of fibre type and initial ΔK range (12-33 MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$). Metallographic and fractographic studies conducted on both the as-received and heat treated specimens after fatigue testing at an initial ΔK of 25 MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$, have shown that fracture in the heat treated material was preceded by extensive crack tip bifurcation which ultimately triggered a sudden burst of fibre failures and subsequent catastrophic failure. Similar features were observed

in the as-received material and both metallographic and fractographic observations would tend to suggest a crack path morphology comparable to that in the heat treated condition. It has been observed that specimens tested near the 'arrest /failure' threshold exhibit extreme secondary cracking, crack tip bifurcation and in extreme circumstances delamination along fibre matrix interfaces. The as-received and 950°C heat treated SM1140+ material exhibited a very similar fatigue crack growth response in that the crack path morphologies of the materials were essentially the same with little difference in the extent of crack tip bifurcation and secondary cracking.

Figure 2. S.E.M. micrographs illustrating the nature of the reaction products formed at the fibre matrix interface in (a) SM1140+ and (b) SM1240 SiC reinforced Ti-6Al-4V during thermal exposure at temperatures of 1100°C and 1070°C respectively

Figure 3. Typical da/dN vs crack length curves for SM1140+ and SM1240 SiC reinforced Ti-6Al-4V composites. (Initial nominal ΔK values calculated for the unbridged defect are also given in the figure)

The results of fatigue crack growth studies are summarised in table 1. Typical fatigue crack growth, da/dN vs crack length curves indicating the effect of initial ΔK are reproduced in figure 3. In general, for both composite materials, the lower levels of applied stress intensity factor range result in a decrease in crack growth rate (da/dN) with increasing crack length, despite the increase in nominal ΔK . This fatigue crack growth response is characteristic of continuous fibre reinforced

MMCs and is a consequence of the effective transfer of load from the matrix to the fibre. This will result in a lower driving force (ΔK) for crack growth in the matrix. If load bearing fibres do not fail when the crack grows around them, the fibres will effectively bridge the crack. As the stress level is increased more load will transfer to the fibres resulting in an increased probability of fibre failure. Table 1 indicates that based on the limiting values of initial ΔK applied values, that for the SM1140+ system a progressive increase in fatigue crack growth resistance is obtained from the as received condition to heat treatments at temperatures of 1030 and 1070°C, with crack arrest now being recorded at initial ΔK levels up to 31 MPa \sqrt{m} for the latter heat treatment. In sharp contrast such elevated heat treatment temperatures degrade the fatigue crack growth resistance of the SM1240 system significantly. Now catastrophic failure has been observed at ΔK values of 14MPa \sqrt{m} in less than 25000 cycles. In this series of tests the fatigue crack growth resistance of the SM1140+ system appears to be superior to the SM1240 system in all conditions. The acute differences in the crack growth response of the SM1140+ and SM1240 material following heat treatment at and above temperatures of 1030°C appear to be best interpreted in terms of both the interfacial reaction layer between the fibre and the matrix, the extent of matrix modification and earlier fibre failure. As indicated in figure 2 large differences were observed in the nature and extent of the reaction zones formed at fibre matrix interfaces. An characteristic of the SM1240 material observed was the development of a duplex reaction layer consisting of an inner TiB₂ layer surrounded by a network of interlocking TiB needles extending into the matrix.

Figure 4(a) The fracture surface, of the SM1240 composite after heat treatment at 1030°C, and tested at an initial $\Delta K=25$ MPa \sqrt{m} .

Figure 4(a) and 4(b) illustrate the great complexity of the fatigue crack growth process in these materials. Indeed in figure 4(a) there are three distinct regions (A, B and C). Region A demonstrates fibre interfacial cracks, and which plausibly result in matrix crack growth away from the fibre and prior to the arrival of the main fatigue crack growing from the unbridged notch. This is consistent with the faceted growth observed, region B, because in titanium alloys such features are seen at relatively low values of ΔK , and may well have occurred prior to the arrival of the main fatigue crack. Metallographic sections away from the fracture plane confirm this interpretation[9]. The third region, C, is of striated growth. The local growth rate measured from striations is in the order of $4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/cycle and would tend to suggest an effective ΔK value of approximately 28 MPa \sqrt{m} [5]. This is comparable with the nominal ΔK value applied, excluding any crack bridging, of 29 MPa \sqrt{m} and is consistent with limited crack bridging and/or prior matrix crack growth in faceted regions. In contrast in figure 4(b) no evidence of the features in regions A and B are seen.

Striation spacings are much smaller in region C and give a local crack growth rate of less than 1.10^{-4} mm/cycle. Such crack growth rates suggest an effective ΔK value of approximately 20 MPa \sqrt{m} compared with a nominal ΔK value applied of 30 MPa \sqrt{m} . In this case, extensive fibre bridging can be deduced, and indeed eventually crack arrest conditions result for this specimen. Further work is required to quantify the reasons for the poor fatigue crack growth resistance of the SM1240 system after heat treatment at temperatures of 1030°C and above. Possible factors include: (a) a reduction of fibre strength, (b) an increase in interfacial strength and (c) the local reduction in matrix load bearing area by additional matrix crack growth from the reaction zone. Further work is required to identify the controlling factors but evidence suggests that the improvements in crack growth behaviour observed in the SM1140+ system may be attributed to temperature induced microstructural changes. Heat treatments resulting in reductions in the volume fraction of primary alpha and coarsening of the transformed beta would be expected to have a major influence on the crack growth characteristics of the metal matrix. In the present instance heat treatment at a temperature of 1030 and 1070°C were found to promote crack branching and secondary cracking within the metal matrix and at the fibre matrix interface.

Figure 4(b) The fracture surface of the SM1140+ composite after heat treatment at 1030°C, and tested at an initial $\Delta K=27$ MPa \sqrt{m} .

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Quantitative metallographic studies have revealed distinct changes in the microstructural morphology of SiC reinforced Ti-6Al-4V compared to conventional monolithic Ti-6Al-4V. Large shifts in the beta transus approach curve were observed for the composite materials with the beta transus temperature increasing from approximately 1005°C for monolithic material to in excess of 1050°C for the composite.
- 2) Distinct reaction layers characteristic to the fibre coating layers have been observed. The SM1140+ reinforced material was characterised by blocky titanium carbides extending around the carbon coating layer at the interface with the metal matrix. In contrast the SM1240 reinforced material was characterised by the development of a duplex reaction layer, consisting of an inner compact titanium diboride layer surrounded by a network of interlocking titanium boride needles which extend into the matrix.

3) Under all conditions the SM1140+ reinforced material exhibited a superior fatigue crack growth response to that measured for the SM1240 reinforced material. As the heat treatment temperature was raised to 1030°C the fatigue crack growth performance of the 1240 reinforced material deteriorated and that of the SM1140+ reinforced material was enhanced. The deterioration in the fatigue crack growth performance of the SM1240 reinforced material after being heat treated at or above a temperature of 1030 °C could be caused by several factors: (a) a reduction in fibre strength, (b) an increase in interfacial strength and (c) the local reduction in matrix load bearing area by additional matrix crack growth from the reaction zone, and/or a combination of these factors. The fatigue crack growth response of the SM1140+ reinforced material when heated at or above a temperature of 1030°C appears to be enhanced by the promotion of crack tip deflection and bifurcation within the metal matrix.

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